

Detection and quantification of some banned colours in common Indian spices with the help of UV-Visible spectrophotometer

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Abstract : A simple and fast spectrophotometric method was developed for qualitative and quantitative detection of three banned colourants viz. metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange in raw foodstuffs. All these colours are hazardous dyes and are commonly used as adulterants in turmeric powder, aniseed, saffron and other food products resembling yellow, green and orange colour. In the present work, metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange were quantified in various raw food samples using a double beam spectrophotometer, which does not require prior analyte separation. Linearities was found to be ($r > 0.995-0.998$) for these colourants, intra-day and inter-day precision (RSD, %) was found less than 1.00, limit of detection and limit of quantification was also calculated for method validation. The simplicity of developed validated method proved to be easy and fast for the detection of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange in raw food samples.

Keywords : UV-Visible spectrophotometry, metanil yellow, malachite green, methyl orange, foodstuffs.

Introduction

Colour is the first sensory quality by which food is judged^{1,2}. Food colours are very important ingredient in various food products, as without its use these products would not tempt and appear desirable. The term colour additive can be applied to any dye, pigment or other substance made or obtained from a vegetable, animal or another source that is capable of colouring food³. Food colours, natural or synthetic, are commonly added to foodstuff in order to improve the colour and to provide a desired appearance. Synthetic colours, which are being used, are of two types, viz. permitted and banned (non permitted). Permitted colours are safe for human consumption, while non permitted colours are potentially toxic. But to our surprise these are still widely used all over the world because of their low price, effectiveness and stability⁴. Mostly banned colours are harmful to human consumption and can cause a number of allergic

reactions⁵⁻⁷. In India the use of synthetic colours in foodstuffs is regulated by Prevention of Food Adulteration Act (PFA)⁸.

Metanil yellow (3-(4-anilinophenylazo)benzene sulfonic acid), malachite green (4-[(4-dimethylaminophenyl) phenyl-methyl]-*N,N*-dimethylaniline) and methyl orange (*p*-[[*p*-(dimethylamino)phenyl]azo]benzenesulfonic acid) are banned colours that are most commonly used in adulteration of foodstuffs because of the obvious reason of their basic colour range i.e. yellow, green and orange. Physical properties of these dyes are given in Table 1. Regular consumption of these dyes can cause poisoning and health hazards like irritation in gastro-intestinal track, cancer, testicular degeneration, anemia, abnormalities in thyroid etc.^{9,10}. LD₅₀ of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange are 60 mg/kg, 80 mg/kg and 60 mg/kg respectively¹¹⁻¹³. Metanil yellow is being used as an adulterant mostly in turmeric (haldi) powder to reduce the

Table 1. Physical properties of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange

Name	Chemical name	Formula	Mol. Wt.	λ_{\max}	Structure
Metanil yellow	(3-(4-Anilinophenylazo)-benzene sulfonic acid sodium salt	$C_{18}H_{14}N_3NaO_3S$	375	427	
Malachite green	(4-[(4-Dimethylaminophenyl)-phenyl-methyl]-N,N-dimethylaniline)	$C_{23}H_{25}ClN_2$	365	624	
Methyl orange	(p-[[p-(Dimethylamino)phenyl]-azo]benzenesulfonic acid sodium salt)	$C_{14}H_{14}N_3NaO_3S$	327	454	

manufacturing cost of packed turmeric powder and to give extra yellowish appearance to it. Malachite green is added in aniseed (saunf) to give enhanced green colour. Methyl orange is used to make fake saffron (kesar) by colouring the dried stigmas of some flowers. As these colours are very harmful for human consumption, there is an urgent need of developing fast and reliable detection technique, which is portable and easy to handle.

During literature survey it was found that detection of these banned colours was performed using different analytical techniques like high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC) was employed for the detection of metanil yellow, sudan dyes in turmeric, chili and curry powders¹⁴, UV-Visible spectrophotometry was used for the detection of methyl orange, tartrazine in commercial saffron products¹⁵, synthetic colours in confectionary products and instant drink powders¹⁶, sudan dyes in various spices by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)¹⁷. But the growing adulteration market demands a need of a rapid, cheap and convenient technique for the detection of these colours in raw food samples or spices, which does not involve much chemicals and heavy instrumentation.

UV-Visible spectrophotometry is one of the useful techniques available for the detection of coloured compounds. It is used in analytical chemistry for the identification of substances through the spectrum absorbed or emitted by them¹⁸. In this technique, a substance's interaction with different wavelengths in a given region of electromagnetic radiation is studied^{19,20}. Visible spectroscopy is the study of interaction of radiation in the visible region ($\lambda = 380\text{--}720\text{ nm}$) of the electromagnetic spectrum^{21,22}. Quantifying the interaction of visible light with

a chemical sample allows the determination of an unknown solution, this phenomena was used for detection of unknown colours in various food products.

Materials and methods :

Instrument :

A double beam spectrophotometer used was Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer UV-210 (Kyoto, Japan), having spectral range of 180–800 nm. The data obtained were processed with the system software (Shimadzu workstation UV software), version 4.52. Weighing machine used was CY204 Digital Balance, Citizen Scale Inc (NJ, USA). Vortex shaker was manufactured by Electrolab India (Mumbai, India) and sonification unit was from Citizen Scale (I) Private Limited (Mumbai, India).

Materials and reagents :

Metanil yellow and malachite green in pure form were purchased from Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. (Mumbai, India). Methyl orange was purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). HPLC grade water was purchased from Rankem, Ranbaxy Fine Chemicals Ltd. (New Delhi, India). All solvents and reagents used were of analytical grade. All solutions were prepared in HPLC grade water and filtered through 0.45 μm nylon membrane filter from Whatman International Ltd. (Maidstone, England).

Standard stock solution preparation :

Stock solutions of standards of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange were prepared by dissolving 10 mg of standard colour in 100 ml of HPLC grade water (100 ppm). For each colour sample, a working series of 10 different concentrations i.e. 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20 ppm was prepared carefully from stock solution. All the samples were filtered through 0.45

μm nylon membrane filter and were kept in refrigerator at 4 °C.

Real sample procurement :

Five samples of turmeric namely A, B, C, D and E of different registered and non registered trademarks were purchased from local market. The samples of turmeric were of Ramdev brand (Ramdev Food Products Pvt. Ltd., Ahmedabad, India), Bilaiya brand (Bilaiya Rang, Sagar, India), Goldiee brand (Goldiee Masale Pvt. Ltd., Kanpur, India), Ruchi brand (Ruchi Spices, Kanpur, India) and Gokul brand (Gokul Grah Udyog, Delhi, India).

Five aniseed samples namely A, B, C, D and E were procured from local restaurants and general stores, which did not have any trademark or brand name. Saffron samples of different non registered trademarks were procured from general stores and super markets for determining the adulteration of methyl orange. All above mentioned samples were specifically collected from Bhopal and Sagar city of Madhya Pradesh and Jhansi and Varanasi city of Uttar Pradesh of India.

Real sample preparation :

The commercially available turmeric samples were selected, weighed and dissolved in HPLC grade water to obtain a concentration of 10 ppm. Aniseed and saffron samples were kept overnight in HPLC grade water for the maximum extraction of colour from them. The extracted colour was diluted with HPLC grade water to obtain a known concentration. All samples were filtered through 0.45 μm nylon membrane filter before placing in spectrophotometer.

Real sample analysis :

To identify the unknown colour adulterant present in procured samples, the samples were analyzed in spectrophotometric system. The spectra thus obtained were then compared with spectra of known standard colour samples which had the probability to match with the unknown samples. Five different samples of each turmeric, aniseed and saffron were analyzed for detecting the presence of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange respectively, based on the results obtained from the preliminary chemical tests conducted in our laboratory and information obtained from reliable sources and data. The calibration curve was used for quantitative analysis.

Results and discussion

Selection of absorbance maxima for standard colours :

To obtain the spectra of standard colours, each standard colour was analyzed using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. A scan was plotted from 180 nm to 800 nm separately for all three standard colours. For selection of wavelength in the visible region, complimentary colour was taken in account.

Standard of metanil yellow showed two prominent absorbances in scan plotted from 180 nm to 800 nm. 427 nm was recorded as maximum absorbance, as observed in Fig. 1. This was also confirmed theoretically, as yellow colour comes under the range of 400–435 nm of visible region. Thus 427 nm was concluded as maximum absorbance for metanil yellow.

Fig. 1. Combined spectra of standard metanil yellow (a), malachite green (b) and methyl orange (c).

While screening malachite green, single absorbance was recorded at 625 nm (Fig. 1). This was also verified theoretically, as blue-green colour falls in the range of 595–750 nm of the visible region. Thus 625 nm was preferred as absorbance maxima for malachite green.

The same procedure was applied for methyl orange also. An absorbance maximum was found at 454 nm (Fig. 1). It was also justified by the fact that yellow-orange colour comes under the range of 435–490 nm, and use of 454 nm was also reported by other researchers²³. Thus, 454 nm was concluded as maximum absorbance for methyl orange. Combined spectra of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange obtained from spectrophotometer is shown in Fig. 1.

Repeatability study :

Repeatability was performed for all standard colours and colours extracted from procured food samples to determine whether the spectra obtained shows difference in absorbance maxima or not. Each colour was analyzed five times in spectrophotometer. Results indicate that absorbance maxima had negligible effect in terms of time.

Limit of detection and limit of quantification :

Solutions of standards of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange were prepared (ten different concentrations i.e. 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 and 20 ppm of each colour) and absorbance were measured in triplicate. In order to determine the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ), concentrations of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange in the lower part of the linear range of the calibration curve were used. The LOD and the LOQ were calculated by using the following equations : $LOD = 3.3 (\sigma/S)$ and $LOQ = 10 (\sigma/S)$, respectively, where σ is the standard deviation of the intercept and S is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve. Results are summarized in Table 2. Calibration curve of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange are given in Figs. 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

Table 2. Slope, intercept, correlation coefficient, limit of detection and quantification (ppm) for standard metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange

Compd.	Slope	Intercept	Correlation coefficient	LOD	LOQ
Metanil yellow	0.038	0.013	0.998	0.04	0.14
Malachite green	0.065	0.021	0.995	0.07	0.21
Methyl orange	0.058	0.019	0.997	0.06	0.18

Fig. 2. Calibration curve of standard metanil yellow concentration against absorption.

Fig. 3. Calibration curve of standard malachite green concentration against absorption.

Accuracy and precision :

The precision of the developed method was determined by replicate analysis of three separate solutions of the working standards at three concentration levels of each colour. Intra-day precision was evaluated by measuring, in triplicate, three different samples at the same concentration under the same experimental condition on the same day, according to the sample preparation method described previously. The precision was calculated from the results obtained by the earliest analysis of samples with the same three concentrations (4, 6 and 8 ppm, $n = 3$). Results are summarized in Table 3.

Fig. 4. Calibration curve of standard methyl orange concentration against absorption.

Table 3. Intra-day and inter-day precision (RSD %, $n = 3$) at three different concentrations (ppm) : $C_1 = 4$, $C_2 = 6$, $C_3 = 8$ ppm for metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange

Colour	Intra-day RSD %			Inter-day RSD %		
	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_1	C_2	C_3
Metanil yellow	0.49	0.60	0.78	0.54	0.73	0.67
Malachite green	0.69	0.84	0.73	0.81	0.56	0.72
Methyl orange	0.23	0.59	0.85	0.90	0.73	0.86

Application of the developed method :

Determination of metanil yellow in turmeric samples :

Five samples of each turmeric powder of various registered and non registered trademarks namely A, B, C, D and E were analyzed using spectrophotometer. The spectra obtained were compared with the spectra of standard metanil yellow for absorbance. It was found that 3 out of 5 spectra of procured turmeric samples i.e. sample B, D and E resembles with the spectra obtained from standard metanil yellow, proving that they are adulterated with metanil yellow. Concentration of metanil yellow present in turmeric samples were estimated from the calibration curve of standard colourant previously obtained from spectrophotometer (Table 4). One positive spectra of procured turmeric sample B is given in Fig. 5.

Table 4. Concentration of metanil yellow found in various turmeric powder samples

Sample	Concentration
Turmeric A	0
Turmeric B	8.99 ppm
Turmeric C	0
Turmeric D	4.75 ppm
Turmeric E	2.43 ppm

Fig. 5. Spectra of turmeric powder sample B.

Table 5. Concentration of malachite green found in various aniseed samples

Sample	Concentration
Aniseed A	3.15 ppm
Aniseed B	5.77 ppm
Aniseed C	0
Aniseed D	0
Aniseed E	0

Determination of malachite green in aniseed samples :

Among five samples (A, B, C, D and E) of aniseed that were procured and analyzed using spectrophotometer, sample A and B showed similar spectra as that of standard malachite green, indicating presence of malachite green in them. Quantification was done using calibration curve (Table 5). Spectra thus obtained, is given in Fig. 6 of aniseed sample A.

Fig. 6. Spectra of aniseed sample A.

Table 6. Concentration of methyl orange found in different fake saffron samples

Sample	Concentration
Saffron A	4.55 ppm
Saffron B	0
Saffron C	0
Saffron D	1.95 ppm
Saffron E	6.67 ppm

Determination of methyl orange in saffron samples :

Five samples of saffron (A, B, C, D and E) were analyzed using spectrophotometer. 3 spectra obtained from saffron samples A, D and E were same as the spectra given by standard methyl orange indicating the presence of methyl orange in them. Concentration of methyl orange found in saffron samples was calculated as above mentioned (Table 6). The positive spectra obtained from saffron sample A is given in Fig. 7.

Conclusion

The proposed spectrophotometric method can be useful in the area of food quality control to detect and quantify these harmful, banned colours in different raw foods. The procedure could also be extended to the analysis of these compounds, used for adulteration purposes. From

the method developed here, it could be concluded that the spectrophotometric procedure can be used for detecting presence of metanil yellow, malachite green and methyl orange in raw food samples, without any massive instrumentation. The method was successfully applied to turmeric, aniseed and saffron samples. Validation including repeatability and precision was done efficiently with satisfactory results and used for assaying these compounds

Fig. 7. spectra of saffron sample A.

in food samples. The method is sensitive enough to undertake fast screening analysis of the compound.

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